

THE ROLE OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN AGRICULTURE

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Abstract. *In this article, we will describe the practical benefits of English for agrarians in the present and near future. This paper presents a needs analysis that explored the English language requirements of agricultural technicians in Chile. It also examined how these needs are perceived by actors involved in agricultural industries and actors involved in the education of this group. Using a qualitative approach, data were elicited from document analysis and interviews with five technicians at one company and five teachers at one VET school. Findings revealed that English language was necessary for technicians to carry out specific tasks. All teachers agreed that their students should be taught not only general English, but also English that is relevant to the students' interests and needs. However, the non-existence of vocational language programs makes it difficult for English teachers to teach the contents pertinent to their students' specialization. This study contributes to an understanding of the relevance of the English language for learners in a specialized context.*

Key words: *Foreign languages, technological discoveries, agricultural sector, social circle, phenomena, expansion, significant meeting, polyglot, memory training*

РОЛЬ ИНОСТРАННЫХ ЯЗЫКОВ В СЕЛЬСКОМ ХОЗЯЙСТВЕ

Аннотация. *В данной статье мы расскажем о практической пользе английского языка для аграриев в настоящем и ближайшем будущем. В этом документе представлен анализ потребностей, в ходе которого изучались требования к английскому языку для сельскохозяйственных техников в Чили. Также было изучено, как эти потребности воспринимаются субъектами, вовлеченными в сельскохозяйственные отрасли, и субъектами, занимающимися образованием этой группы. Используя качественный подход, данные были получены из анализа документов и интервью с пятью техниками в одной компании и пятью учителями в одном профессиональном училище. Выводы показали, что английский язык был необходим техническим специалистам для выполнения определенных задач. Все преподаватели согласились с тем, что их ученикам следует обучать не только общему английскому языку, но и английскому языку, соответствующему интересам и потребностям учащихся. Однако отсутствие профессиональных языковых программ затрудняет для учителей английского языка преподавание содержания, относящегося к специализации их студентов. Это исследование способствует пониманию актуальности английского языка для учащихся в специализированном контексте.*

Ключевые слова: *Иностранные языки, технологические открытия, аграрный сектор, круг общения, явления, экспансия, знаменательная встреча, полиглот, тренировка памяти.*

INTRODUCTION

Globalization in the world of work and the continued use of English has meant an increase in the demand for language courses addressing occupational and/or workplace needs. In Uzbekistan, agriculture is an important occupational sector, which has benefitted, in the last two decades, from globalization and international trade agreements. These agreements have meant

not only international integration for the country (arrangement among countries and regions such as Russia and Central Asia that comprises the reduction of barriers to trade, see, but also the need for developing English language skills on the part of agricultural professionals.

Generally, technicians provide technical support in agricultural production, agricultural machinery and supplies, and technical supervision of agrochemicals, and provide quality control, inter alia. They are versatile professionals and their roles, responsibilities, job positions, and work areas vary according to their technical knowledge and skills, experience, and studies. For example, in terms of education, Uzbekistan offers vocational education and training (VET) programs in agriculture at the secondary and tertiary level. Secondary school VET programs provide students with specialized training in the field, prepare them for the world of work, and foster continuity of post-secondary studies. Post-secondary VET programs provide students with high-level technical and specialized knowledge and skills and enhance leadership skills. Secondary school graduates can work as mid-level technicians if they obtain a secondary VET certificate, which is awarded only to those who fulfil a minimum requirement. Post-secondary graduates can work as high-level technicians if they obtain a post-secondary VET professional or technical degree.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

It makes no sense to pour platitudes about how learning a foreign language, and especially English, opens new doors and horizons for a person. All of this is great, but it doesn't motivate or describe real, direct benefits.

1 reason - the study of professional literature

Russian-language and Uzbek-language pages on the Internet account for less than 30% of the total. And it's not even about the statistics and the total amount of information that can be found. Why foreign languages are needed is to read serious scientific papers, studies, books, information about new technological discoveries, including in the agricultural sector. And they are published primarily in English. It may seem that sooner or later they will be translated into their native language, but this is a delusion. Much of the latest, most relevant and valuable professional information exists only in English.

2 reason - expanding horizons and social circle

Speakers of several languages will not let you lie - sometimes they have thoughts in a secondary language. At the same time, for some reason, such thoughts and discoveries do not come to mind in their native language. By learning a language, a person willy-nilly adopts the culture of another people, expands his ideas about people and phenomena. What is useful to learn foreign languages is the constant expansion of horizons and circle of communication. New, interesting and useful people come into life, communication with which was previously impossible. And in business, the right contact can change lives forever.

Reason 3 - Increased value and greater potential in the eyes of the employer's company

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

How many languages do you need to know to get a job in a large international company? At least two. And the more languages a specialist knows, the greater his significance and value for the company. If he is the only one who knows Spanish or German, he will be sent to a significant meeting. In Ukraine, knowing English has the same effect. Specialists who know him almost always occupy higher positions and receive higher salaries.

Polyglots always know where to go to work with knowledge of a foreign language and are never left without an interesting task. Such a person will find a vacancy in almost any company. If he is also a highly qualified specialist, they will fight for his hire, increase the proposed salary and offer more comfortable working conditions.

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4 reason - the development of intelligence and memory training

Replenishment of knowledge in such an area as language and social communication significantly affects the pace of professional, intellectual and personal development of a person. And in the age of information technology and information overload, memory training is extremely important.

Pocket devices, convenient programs, applications and reminders provoke the brain to save energy. He refrains from trying to remember anything, as a smart alarm clock will always remind you of an important event. Learning a foreign language perfectly helps not only to stop the degradation of memory, but also to develop it.

Reason 5 - freedom from translators and comfort when visiting other countries

CONCLUSION

A business trip or vacation moves to a whole new level when you know English and can use it at least at an intermediate level. With a foreign language, a person can always independently book a hotel, rent a car, ask for directions and talk with representatives of another culture. Communication is the richest source of information, so any trip will be brighter and more memorable.

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